

Technical note : configuration and first evaluation of the kilometre-scale regional climate model CNRM-AROME46t1

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1 Introduction

The AROME limited-area, convection-permitting model was first used in operational numerical weather prediction (NWP) at Météo-France in 2008 (Seity et al., 2011). AROME combines a non-hydrostatic dynamical core from the ALADIN model (Bénard et al., 2010) with physical parameterisations from the Meso-NH research model (Lac et al., 2018).

Starting in 2014, CNRM-AROME was adopted as a convection-permitting regional climate model (CP-RCM) at the Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques (CNRM) for high-resolution climate simulations. The model was first employed in climate studies over a south east France domain by (Fumière et al., 2020), based on development cycle 38. In 2018, work began on CNRM-AROME cycle 41. The reference paper for this cycle is (Caillaud et al., 2021). Simulations were performed over larger domains: the common pan-alpine domain defined through the CORDEX Flagship Pilot Study (FPS) on convection program (Coppola et al., 2020) and the north west Europe domain defined in the framework of the EUCP (European Climate Prediction System, <https://www.eucp-project.eu>) project (Caillaud et al. (2021); Lucas-Picher et al. (2024b)). The AROME model is also used for climate studies by the HCLIM community (Belušić

et al., 2020).

This technical note presents the cy46t1 of CNRM-AROME used in climate studies starting in 2024. From 2022 to 2024, development cycle 46 was also used for NWP at the French national weather service. For complementary information on the climate version of CNRM-AROME cy46t1, the reference document for this cycle is (Quenum et al., 2026). Compared to earlier AROME versions used in climate studies, several modifications have been introduced in cy46t1, especially in the surface configuration. When possible, the climate version of AROME applies options and parameterisations from its operational NWP version. However, for the surface, this version of the AROME climate model uses advances in surface schemes developed for two other CNRM climate models, CNRM-ALADIN (Nabat et al., 2020) and CNRM-CM6 (Voldoire et al., 2019). Due to their short time frames and use of data assimilation, NWP models may use surface schemes that are ill-adapted for the time scales of the climate. In particular, a more complex urban scheme was added to CNRM-AROME cy46t1, enabling the modelisation of vegetation within the urban canyon and building energy use. After an initial presentation of the CNRM-AROME model, the second part of this note will present results from the CNRM-AROME cy46t1 evaluation simulation forced by the ERA5 reanalysis over a 2.5 km extended pan-alpine domain (ALPX-3).

2 Cycle 46t1 of the CNRM-AROME CP-RCM

CNRM-AROME follows development cycles determined by collaborations between the CNRM, the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) and the ACCORD consortium of 26 countries. The source code for AROME is also sometimes referred to as the "common code" because it is shared between the models AROME, ALADIN, ARPEGE (global) and the Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) used by the ECMWF. Different models are accessed by using different physics and model geometries in the namelist.

The number of the development cycle is followed by a letter, 't' for Toulouse, indicating that this is the version of the code used by Météo-France, which is located in the city of Toulouse, France. Conversely, the same cycle used for running the IFS model at the ECMWF would be labelled cy46r1, where the 'r' is for Reading.

This document details the use of the common code to run CNRM-AROME cy46t1 in a climate configuration.

2.1 Model Dynamics and Physics

The AROME model operates on a non-hydrostatic, bi-spectral, fully compressible system of equations discretized using a semi-implicit, semi-Lagrangian numerical scheme. This scheme allows the model to be computationally efficient, but increases its effective resolution (Ricard et al., 2013). The horizontal resolution of CNRM-AROME is 2.5 km. The vertical structure is represented by 60 vertical levels, from 10 meters above the surface to 1 hPa, with a denser distribution of levels within the atmospheric boundary layer. Comparatively, at Météo-France, AROME cy46t1 NWP uses 90 vertical levels for a resolution of 1.3 km. To maintain numerical stability and a reasonable computational cost, the CNRM-AROME

simulation in this study uses a 60s time step.

For dynamics, compared to AROME cy41t1 (Caillaud et al., 2021), the only difference is that AROME cy46t1 uses conservative semi-Lagrangian (SL) interpolators and removes the semi-Lagrangian horizontal diffusion schema (SLHD). This modification improves the representation of diurnal convection under conditions of weak synoptic-scale forcing. To avoid unrealistic precipitation and divergent winds near convective cells, the COMAD correction ((Malardel and Ricard, 2015)) to the SL transport scheme is maintained in AROME cy46t1. The different physical parameterisations are summarised in Table 1. These have remained unchanged from cycle 41. Deep convection is explicitly resolved by model dynamics at the model’s horizontal resolution of 2.5 km, while shallow convection is still parameterised. The constant for subgrid condensation is increased from the NWP value in order to address the underestimation of summer convective cloud formation (Lucas-Picher et al., 2024b). This improves cloud formation in undersaturated conditions and the corresponding incoming shortwave radiation (Lemonsu et al., 2023).

CNRM-AROME cy46t1 does not use interactive aerosols and only the direct effect of the aerosols is considered, namely the aerosol-radiation interactions. No effect of aerosols on cloud microphysics is included. The aerosol forcing is described in section 3.4.

Table 1: AROME physical parameterisations, reproduced from (Caillaud et al., 2021).

Parameterisations	Scheme	Reference
Turbulence	CBR scheme based on a prognostic equation of TKE	(Cuxart et al., 2000; Bougeault and Lacarrere, 1989)
Shallow convection and clouds	PMMC09 scheme based on the eddy diffusivity mass flux (EDMF) approach Statistical cloud scheme	(Pergaud et al., 2009) (Bechtold et al., 1995)
Microphysics and sedimentation	ICE3, one-moment microphysics prognostic scheme with five prognostic variables of water condensates (cloud droplets, rain, ice crystals, snow and graupel). Hail is not activated. Sedimentation scheme	(Pinty and Jabouille, 1998) (Lascaux et al., 2006) (Bouteloup et al., 2011)
Radiation	Version of the ECMWF radiation parameterisations (RRTMG: 16 bands for longwave and FMR: 6 bands for shortwave)	(Iacono et al., 2008; Mlawer et al., 1997; Fouquart and Bonnel, 1980; Morcrette, 2001)

2.2 Surface and Land-Atmosphere Interactions

CNRM-AROME cy46t1 is coupled to the SURFEX land surface platform, version 8.0, compared to version 7.3 for CNRM-AROME cy41t1 (Masson et al., 2013). This technical note reproduces the principal modifications applied to cy46, which are also described in the reference paper (Quenum et al., 2026). In particular, this section seeks to highlight the updates made to the surface scheme relative to CNRM-AROME cy41t1, which is

described in detail in (Caillaud et al., 2021).

Each surface grid cell is discretised into four land-cover tiles (i.e. nature, urban, continental waters, and ocean) each associated with dedicated schemes. Processes over the nature tile are represented using the interaction soil-biosphere-atmosphere (ISBA) land surface model (Noilhan and Planton, 1989; Boone et al., 1999). In this study, we employ the configuration described and evaluated in (Monteiro et al., 2024), referred to as ISBA-DIF-ES. This configuration relies on a diffusion-based soil scheme (Boone et al., 2000; Decharme et al., 2011), which explicitly resolves soil moisture and heat transfer over 14 layers down to a depth of 12 m, with refined vertical resolution near the surface. Earlier versions of CNRM-AROME (Caillaud et al., 2021) instead used the ISBA-3L force-restore scheme, which relaxes soil heat and moisture toward bulk values in two thermal and three hydrological layers after accounting for surface fluxes (Noilhan and Planton, 1989).

The natural covers can be initially described according to 19 different functional types, to which are associated physical and physiological properties (e.g., leaf area index, root depth and profile, stomatal resistance) defined in the ECOCLIMAP database (see Section 2.3). These functional types are gathered into three patches (bare soil, low vegetation, high vegetation), each with averaged properties, in order to compute separate energy and water balances at the subgrid scale. In the previous version, only one patch was considered. The transpiration of plants is calculated with a stomatal resistance according to the approach of (Jarvis, 1976). In order to improve the dynamics of soil temperature in ISBA, an insulating effect due to leaf litter or mulch is included by adjusting the thermal conductivity of the first soil layers (Le Moigne et al., 2009).

The ISBA-DIF-ES configuration also employs the multi-layer ES (explicit snow) snow scheme (Boone and Etchevers, 2001; Decharme et al., 2016), which solves a dedicated energy and mass balance for a 12-layer snowpack, replacing the single-layer parameterisation implemented in CNRM-AROME cy41t1 (Douville et al., 1995). Additional modifications include the GFLUX parameterisation, which improves the simulation of snowmelt over partially snow-covered nature tiles by reducing soil-snow heat exchange. The snow cover fraction over vegetated areas has been adjusted to increase more rapidly with snow accumulation by reducing the W_{sn} parameter from 5 to 1 (see eq. 5 from (Monteiro et al., 2024) for further details). Glaciers are not explicitly represented; instead, snow depth is capped at 33.3 m to avoid unrealistically tall “snow towers” that could form in previous CNRM-AROME versions (Decharme et al., 2016; Monteiro et al., 2022). A detailed description of these developments and their beneficial impacts on simulation performance is provided in (Monteiro et al., 2024), where the authors evaluated the snowpack and surface options for CNRM-AROME cy46t1 over an Alpine domain. Ultimately, the latter improvements to the surface configuration enable a better representation of surface energy and mass fluxes while aligning more closely with the schemes used in other CNRM models (e.g.: CNRM-ALADIN and CNRM-CM6 (Decharme et al., 2019)), as well as other CP-RCMs similar to AROME, such as HARMONIE-CLIMATE (Belušić et al., 2020; Lind et al., 2020).

The Town Energy Balance (TEB) urban canopy model is used to simulate radiation, energy, water, and momentum exchanges over urban tiles. A simplified urban canyon representation (Masson, 2000) is applied to compute the radiation and energy exchanges between roofs, walls, roads, and the atmosphere, while incorporating key processes such

as radiative trapping, heat storage in urban materials, and anthropogenic heat emissions. Simple urban hydrological processes are considered (Masson, 2000), including water interception by roads and roofs, evaporation of water intercepted by these surfaces, and surface runoff when the maximum interception capacity is exceeded. A new addition to CNRM-AROME cy46t1 is the use of TEB-Veg, which accounts for urban vegetation inside the canyon unlike previous versions of CNRM-AROME (Lemonsu et al., 2012). Urban vegetation is simulated using the physical equations of the ISBA model and coupled with the TEB model to account for radiative and energy interactions between the vegetation and the roads and canyon walls. The present configuration also activates the building energy module (BEM) (Schoetter et al., 2017) which resolves the building internal energy balance for a single thermal zone in order to simulate the evolution of indoor temperature, building energy demand for heating and air-conditioning, and heat exchanges between buildings and the atmosphere. The energy gains in the building result from solar radiation penetrating through the windows; however, internal loads associated with household appliances are not included in this configuration. The mechanisms of energy exchange are air infiltration and ventilation between the outdoor and indoor air. According to French regulation, the setpoint temperatures for heating and cooling are 19°C and 26°C respectively. In the outdoor area, anthropogenic heat emissions from road traffic or industrial activities are not included due to the lack of robust and representative data at the model resolution. BEM and TEB require descriptive parameters of urban areas: land use (proportion of buildings, roads, vegetation), geometry of the average canyon, and thermal and radiative properties of urban materials (roofs, walls, and roads). These are provided by representative urban typologies defined in the ECOCLIMAP-I database described below.

For town and nature tiles, the surface boundary layer prognostic scheme, CANOPY (Hamdi and Masson, 2008; Masson and Seity, 2009), is activated. CANOPY adds additional layers between the first atmospheric level and the surface, enabling the production of more realistic 2 m temperature and 10 m wind fields.

Turbulent land-sea fluxes use the ECUME6 parameterisation, compared to COARE previously (Belamari, 2005; Lfarh et al., 2024). This new parameterisation increases ocean evaporation and improves the representation of the lower atmosphere and Mediterranean heavy precipitation episodes. For continental waters, the Charnock formula (Charnock, 1955) used by CNRM-AROME cy41t1 remains unchanged.

2.3 Land surface datasets

This technical note reproduces the description of land surface datasets in the reference paper by (Quenum et al., 2026).

CNRM-AROME needs surface information to define the fraction of different land cover types over each grid cell, which are then used to derive input parameters for the TEB and ISBA models. Land cover types are provided by the ECOCLIMAP-I global high-resolution (1 km) database (Champeaux, 2005) and are composed of land use and land cover according to 243 classes. Over Europe, ECOCLIMAP-I is based on the CORINE Land Cover (EEA, 2020) database from 1990 and includes nine different urban classes (e.g., urban dense, suburban, commercial and industrial). ECOCLIMAP-I associates a set of descriptive parameters to each class. It incorporates key vegetation parameters required

by ISBA, including leaf area index (LAI) and vegetation fraction, taking into account seasonal variability. Each urban class is described by geometric parameters (height and density of buildings, aspect ratio) and thermal and radiative properties of materials, as well as the density and properties of urban vegetation.

The soil texture maps (fractions of sand, clay, silt) are provided by the global Harmonized World Soil Database (FAO, 2012). Soil, thermal and hydrological properties are derived from pedotransfer functions using this texture information (Clapp and Hornberger, 1978).

The topography is defined using the Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data provided by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) and the National Geospatial-Intelligence Agency (NGA). This database has a native horizontal resolution of 250 m (Carabajal et al., 2011), which is interpolated to the 2.5-km resolution of the CNRM-AROME grid.

3 The ERA5 hindcast simulation

3.1 Description of the simulation

A 67-year CNRM-AROME evaluation simulation (cf. fig. 1) was performed, covering the period from 1959 to 2025 with a two-year spin-up (1957–1958). This was an exceptionally long run for a kilometric climate model. A rerun was performed from 1971 to 1996 due to a problem in the aerosol forcing. The CNRM-AROME evaluation simulation was driven by the ERA5 global reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) at an hourly frequency. The high resolution, large domain size and over 200 hourly output variables came at a high cost. Under ideal conditions, 2.5 days were needed to run one year of the 2.5 km CNRM-AROME model over the domain shown in fig. 1 with 60 vertical levels, which was 9 times longer than the 12.5 km CNRM-ALADIN model over the Euro-CORDEX domain (see section 3.6 for more information on CORDEX) with 91 vertical levels. Accounting for reruns and calculator availability, this simulation took around 10 months to complete.

Figure 1: CNRM-AROME evaluation simulation setup.

3.2 Domain

The limited-area CP-RCM domain was the common extended pan-Alpine domain (ALPX-3) defined through the Impetus4Change European project ((Freisen et al., 2025)), chosen to cover cities of interest within the project framework (Paris, Barcelona, and Prague) and to include the ALP-3 domain defined through the CORDEX flagship pilot study (FPS) on convection program (Coppola et al., 2020). The 2.5 km CNRM-AROME computational domain consisted of 648,000 grid points (900 points of longitude and 720 points of latitude) with a conformal-Lambert projection. The central physical zone (C zone) consisted of 847×667 points, corresponding to around $2100 \text{ km} \times 1700 \text{ km}$ at a 2.5 km resolution. The intermediate zone (I zone), where the lateral boundary conditions were relaxed to the imposed boundary conditions, was composed of 21 grid points on each side of the domain. The extension zone (E zone) on the north and east sides of the domain, an artificial periodic extension of the spectral fields, contained 11 grid points.

Figure 2: Orography of the ALPX-3 domain in meters.

3.3 Lateral, initial and surface boundary conditions

For the CNRM, this was the first time that the ERA5 global reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) was used directly to force AROME without an intermediate nested model. In order

to maintain compatibility with legacy versions of the CNRM common code and because of technical difficulties, ERA5 data were extracted at a 50 km resolution from the tl399 spectral grid. The jump in resolution of a factor 20 may create a “spatial spin-up”, a zone over which boundary effects impact the representation of the atmosphere. Based on Matte et al. (2017), CNRM-AROME should have a spatial spin-up of 120 points (300 km) for a resolution of 2.5 km compared to only 30 points when the lateral forcing is at a resolution of 12.5 km (Caillaud et al., 2021). For the most part, the present study focused on Metropolitan France and was not impacted by the spatial spin-up.

Initial conditions were provided by interpolating ERA5 fields over the entire domain for all model levels at the beginning of the simulation. Between 15 and 20 km above the surface, upper boundary conditions were relaxed back to ERA5 for wind divergence, vorticity and temperature. Using a relaxation with very low coefficients avoided the numerical stability problems that can arise from a low number of vertical levels in the upper troposphere and stratosphere.

Daily sea surface temperatures (SSTs) were produced by interpolating monthly ERA5 SSTs at 31 km (native T639 Gaussian grid) using a quadratic interpolation between 3 months. This conserved the SST monthly mean value.

3.4 Radiative forcing

In addition to water vapour directly simulated by the model, the concentrations of five greenhouse gases were imposed: CO_2 , N_2O , CH_4 , $CFC - 11$ and $CFC - 12$ with one value per year and per species, homogeneous in the spatial dimension. The values were provided by observations before 2014 and by the ssp3-7.0 scenario afterwards (CORDEX, 2021).

An effort was made to select the most relevant aerosol forcing with monthly evolutive two-dimensional maps of dust, sea salt, organic carbon, black carbon, sulfates, nitrates and ammonium. They were provided by the ALDERA4 simulation (Nabat et al., 2020), an evaluation simulation using the RCM CNRM-ALADIN64E1 driven by ERA5 with spectral nudging over an extended Med-CORDEX domain (12.5 km and 91 vertical levels) with interactive aerosols (TACTIC scheme). Aerosol optical depth monthly means from ALDERA4 were added to the AROME restart at the beginning of each month. They remained fixed for the duration of the month.

Volcanic aerosols were provided by the official CMIP6 dataset (Thomason et al., 2018), adapted to the 550 nm aerosol optical density from 1959 to 2014. From 2025 onward, volcanic aerosols were considered to revert back to the 1850-2014 mean. A linear interpolation was used between 2014 (historic inventories) and 2025 (1850-2014 mean).

3.5 Gridded reference data

ANASTASIA (ANalyse Spatiale des TempérAtures de Surface avec Initialisation Aurelhy) is a gridded data product representing the daily minimum and maximum temperature at a 1 km resolution over metropolitan France from 1947 to the present (Besson et al., 2019). The first step of production is a daily quality control of weather station observations applied to remove outliers. The data are then interpolated on a 1 km grid, depending

on daily weather regimes and accounting for the influence of topography on the spatial variability of temperature. Since it is available at high resolution and over a long period, this dataset is currently the best available product for evaluating the ability of the climate model to simulate general features of the temperature over France. Nonetheless, it should not be used to study trends as the number of stations used changes over the period. Furthermore, very few stations are located in cities and representative of the urban climate; therefore, urban effects on temperatures are not properly taken into account.

COMEPHORE (COmbinaison en vue de la Meilleure Estimation de la Precipitation HOraiRE) is a high-resolution gridded dataset of precipitation over metropolitan France (Tabary et al., 2012). It combines radar data and rain gauges to produce hourly rain data at a 1 km resolution over the period from 1997 to the present. COMEPHORE has been shown to be the gridded dataset most well-suited to study extreme precipitation over the French Mediterranean region (Fumière et al., 2020; Caillaud et al., 2021). The main strength of COMEPHORE is that the inclusion of radar data enables the coverage of zones with relatively few stations. The high resolution and radar spatial coverage are particularly interesting for studying localised heavy precipitation. The COMEPHORE dataset shows some temporal inhomogeneities resulting from improvements in calculation methods in 2007 and changes in radar coverage over France. Concerning spatial inhomogeneities, COMEPHORE underestimates the precipitation in mountainous regions above altitudes of 1500 m. High altitude regions are particularly subject to errors in radar measurement, known as masking effects, and also present a lower density of stations and undercatch, which greatly increases in the case of solid precipitation.

3.6 CNRM-ALADIN RCM simulation

To evaluate the potential added value of increasing the resolution, the CNRM-AROME simulation was compared to the CNRM-ALADIN64E1 climate model, a medium resolution regional climate model at 12.5 km with 91 vertical levels on the Euro-CORDEX domain (Nabat et al., 2020). The CNRM-ALADIN model served as the intermediate nest between CNRM-AROME and global climate models for historical and future climate simulations. In the present case, CNRM-AROME and CNRM-ALADIN both used the same lateral boundary conditions produced by ERA5 at a resolution of 50 km, but with a reduced temporal frequency for ALADIN (6 hours compared to 1 hour for AROME). The lower cost of ALADIN enabled the use of a tuning technique to optimise the choice of certain parameter values before running the simulation. This evaluation simulation was compared with the CNRM-AROME evaluation in order to characterise the potential added value of increasing the resolution.

In the next section, the added value of CNRM-AROME over CNRM-ALADIN (following (Caillaud et al., 2021)) is defined as :

$$Added-value_{(AROME,ALADIN)} = |f_{ALADIN} - f_{reference}| - |f_{AROME} - f_{reference}| \quad (1)$$

where f stands for the field. The added value compares the deviation of the two models from a given reference. If $Added-value_{(AROME,ALADIN)}$ is positive (negative), AROME's performance is better (worse) than ALADIN.

At the CNRM, CNRM-ALADIN uses both the Med-CORDEX (ALDERA) and Euro-CORDEX domains in addition to others outside of continental Europe. These

domains are defined by the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX), which is a guiding framework for the regional climate community. More information can be found at <http://cordex.org>.

4 Results over France and the extended Alpine domain

The fields of mean sea level pressure, rainfall, temperature and shortwave downwelling radiation were evaluated for CNRM-AROME cy46 compared to observations and CNRM-ALADIN64E1. The evaluation period went from 1959-2022 when observations were available. The period 2023-2025 was not considered, as it became available after the completion of this document.

4.1 Pressure at sea level

CNRM-AROME was compared to its forcing dataset, ERA5, in order to confirm that results remained coherent with the large scales provided by the reanalysis. In most cases, AROME remained within 0.5 hPa of ERA5 with the exception of a negative bias over the Alps in winter (around 0.5 to 1.5 hPa), a weak positive bias over Central and Eastern Europe in spring (around 0.5 to 1 hPa) and stronger localised biases during the summer over high altitudes. Due to the large resolution difference between ERA5 and AROME, some differences were to be expected in zones of rapidly varying orography.

Figure 3: Seasonal means of air pressure at sea level for AROME compared to ALADIN and to its forcing dataset (ERA5) over the 1959-2022 period.

4.2 Daily minimum and maximum 2m air temperature

The 2 m temperature simulated by the AROME model was compared to gridded observations and to ALADIN over metropolitan France. The seasonal average was taken over the 1959-2022 period for the minimum and maximum daily temperatures. The ANASTASIA product was available only for metropolitan France, so the present evaluation was limited to this scope.

Minimum temperatures simulated by AROME presented low (between $+1.5/-1.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) biases, with an underestimation over most of France in spring. During summer, AROME tended to overestimate minimum temperatures over France, especially over the Mediterranean region. A weaker warm bias was present in autumn. Systematic warm biases were noted over some regions: the forest of the Landes in south west France, the Sologne Forest south of Paris, the Jura Mountains, the Southern Alps, and the Provence and Côte d’Azur regions, with a greater bias in summer. This highlights what could be a weakness in the representation of the surface-atmosphere interactions over specific types of vegetation. Cold biases were found over the Alps and Pyrenees, which were difficult to quantify due to known weaknesses in the observational data. The spatial interpolation method used in ANASTASIA takes into account orography to remap data from stations, but mountainous regions are characterised by a low density of stations and temperature records present stronger biases at high altitudes.

The warm bias over the forest of the Landes is exacerbated in ALADIN, despite a generalised cold bias over France for most seasons. The high resolution AROME simulation created added value over France, most notably over coastal and mountainous regions. During summer, AROME degraded performances in the Northeast of France, increasing warm biases compared to ALADIN. The most notable improvement in performance was over the Alps where ALADIN’s cold bias is around 4°C in most seasons. The yearly averages in fig. 5 confirmed that AROME added value over most regions of France.

For maximum temperatures (fig. 6), AROME exacerbated cold biases compared to ALADIN for all seasons except summer. Performances were most degraded in spring, when AROME showed a $2-3^{\circ}\text{C}$ bias over most of France. Over summer, AROME reduced biases compared to ALADIN, with the use of TEB leading to warm biases over urban areas where cold biases were present in ALADIN. In all seasons, the cold bias over urban areas was reduced, or changed to a warm bias in AROME.

At this stage, it is difficult to conclude about the added-value or limitations of AROME coupled with the TEB urban canopy model above cities due to the lack of representative observations of urban environments in the ANASTASIA reference product. The compensation of warm and cold biases improved model performance over urban areas, but it is unclear if this is for the right reasons. With the exception of summer and the Alpine region where biases were improved, AROME worsened cold biases in maximum 2m temperatures compared to ALADIN.

Compared to the evaluation of the previous version of AROME (Lucas-Picher et al., 2024b), the cold bias in maximum temperature, larger in spring, remained. It was previously associated with a wet bias, but this was not the case in the new simulation. The reasons behind this persistent bias are yet to be fully understood. The systematic warm bias previously present in summer was corrected in this new version of the model for maximum temperature and reduced for minimum temperature.

4.3 Precipitation statistics

The performance of AROME was evaluated using the COMEPHORE dataset over its availability period from 1997 to 2022. AROME accurately represented the general features of the seasonal mean precipitation with low biases of between $-1/+1 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$ (see

Figure 4: Seasonal means of minimum temperatures for ANASTASIA reference, together with the corresponding differences between AROME and ALADIN simulations and observations and the added value of AROME (cf. eq. 1) over the 1959-2022 period. All data have been interpolated onto the lowest resolution grid (i.e. the EUR-12 12.5 km grid).

Figure 5: Yearly means of minimum temperatures for ANASTASIA reference, together with the corresponding differences between AROME and ALADIN simulations and observations and the added value of AROME (cf. eq. 1) over the 1959-2022 period. All data have been interpolated onto the lowest resolution grid (i.e. the EUR-12 12.5 km grid).

Figure 8). Except for systematic dry biases on the tip of Brittany and the south of the Atlantic coast, AROME tended to overestimate precipitation in winter and spring and underestimate it in summer, especially from the centre of France to the Northeast. The weakest biases were in autumn. Over mountainous regions, COMEPHORE does not include an altitude correction and underestimates precipitation for altitudes above 1500 m. AROME also provided the most added value over regions where COMEPHORE was the least reliable, which complicated the validation process.

To study extreme events, the 99th percentile of daily precipitation as well as the 99.9th percentile of hourly precipitation were computed on the ALPX-3 (AROME and COMEPHORE only) and EUR-12 grids (Ban et al., 2020; Caillaud et al., 2021). In both cases, the model performed well in winter and spring and underestimated observed values in summer. In autumn, Southeast France (near the Cevennes) experiences the maximum daily and hourly precipitation associated with Mediterranean heavy precipitation. In this region, the model presented an overestimation at higher altitudes and an underestimation over the foothills, a phenomena exacerbated in ALADIN. For hourly extremes (cf. fig. 12, AROME presented the most added value over the Mediterranean and the southern flank of the Cevennes Mountains, providing improved simulations over the region most impacted by extreme precipitation in France.

Compared to ALADIN, AROME improved extreme precipitation in general over France, though added value was patchy and most noticeable over the Cevennes and Alps. Depending on the season, AROME's performance was slightly worse over the Pyrenees compared to ALADIN. This may be related to the poor quality of the observations over this region and merits further exploration.

Hourly extreme precipitation was calculated only for the AROME model (fig. 12). The model performed well during winter and spring, but once again failed to initiate rainfall early enough after landfall over the coastal Mediterranean region during fall, leading to an overestimation of rainfall at higher altitudes over the Cevennes region and not enough over the coastal plains and foothills. Summer extreme hourly precipitation was underestimated

Figure 7: Yearly means of maximum temperatures for ANASTASIA reference, together with the corresponding differences between AROME and ALADIN simulations and observations and the added value of AROME (cf. eq. 1) over the 1959-2022 period. All data have been interpolated onto the lowest resolution grid (i.e. the EUR-12 12.5 km grid).

in AROME, especially over the Mediterranean region.

When comparing this new simulation to the ones made with the previous version of AROME (Lucas-Picher et al., 2024b), the spring wet bias for mean precipitation has been corrected, but the summer dry bias was exacerbated for both mean and extreme values. The local underestimation of heavy precipitation from the Cevennes foothills to the plains was already present in the previous run (Caillaud et al., 2021) with a bias of the same order, which can be expected since there has been no change in the model regarding this aspect.

4.4 Surface radiation

Shortwave (SW) downwelling radiation were compared with the SARA3-3 satellite data record (Pfeifroth et al., 2024) over the 1983-2022 period (Figure 13). Both quantities were compared on the EUR-12 grid. SARA3-3 was provided on a $0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$ SARA3-3 grid, which was close to the resolution of AROME at mid-latitudes. The AROME SW radiation had a positive bias over high altitudes which was exacerbated in spring and summer and more moderate in autumn and winter. Compared to AROME cy41t1 (Lucas-Picher et al., 2024a), positive biases in downwelling SW radiation were reduced over continental France, often changing the sign of weaker biases from positive to negative. Over mountainous regions, however, biases remained similar to previous versions, indicating that improvements in the surface scheme and modifications to the cloud cover were not effective in improving this behaviour.

Compared to ALADIN, AROME often degraded the SW radiation in high-altitude regions, particularly over the Alps. In Spring and Summer, AROME added value over coastal and ocean grid points near the English Channel, the Mediterranean (concentrated over the Gulf of Lion in Summer and more general in Spring) and the Cantabrian Sea (Summer). As both AROME and ALADIN used forced SST at 31 km issued by ERA5, this difference could not be attributed to different representations of the SST.

Figure 8: Seasonal mean precipitation from the COMEPHORE reference dataset, together with corresponding biases for the ALADIN and AROME simulations and the added value of AROME (cf. eq. 1) over the 1997-2022 period. All datasets were interpolated onto the coarsest spatial resolution, the EUR-12 12 km grid.

Figure 9: Daily precipitation extremes (99th percentile of daily totals) from the COMEPHORE reference dataset, AROME simulations and the AROME bias over the 2.5 km ALPX-3 domain over the 1997-2022 period.

Figure 10: Daily precipitation extremes (99th percentile of daily totals) from the COMEPHORE reference dataset, together with the corresponding biases for the ALADIN and AROME simulations and the added value of AROME (cf. eq. 1) over the 1997-2022 period. All datasets were interpolated onto the coarsest spatial resolution, the EUR-12 12 km grid.

Figure 11: Hourly precipitation extremes (99.9th percentile of hourly totals) from the COMEPHORE reference dataset, AROME simulations and the AROME bias over the 2.5 km ALPX-3 domain over the 1997-2022 period.

Figure 12: Hourly precipitation extremes (99.9th percentile of hourly totals) from the COMEPHORE reference dataset, together with the corresponding biases for the ALADIN and AROME simulations and the added value of AROME (cf. eq. 1) over the 1997-2022 period. All datasets were interpolated onto the coarsest spatial resolution, the EUR-12 12 km grid.

Figure 13: Seasonal mean downwelling SW radiation over the 1983-2022 period. First column : SARAH-3. Second column : seasonal mean bias for ALADIN with respect to SARAH-3. Third column : seasonal mean bias for AROME with respect to SARAH-3. Fourth column : added value of AROME. All data have been interpolated onto the ALADIN 12 km grid.

4.5 Overall performance of AROME and conclusions

This technical note presented the climate version of CNRM-AROME cy46 and some preliminary results over the ALPX-3 and EUR-12 domains. The overall evaluation of the AROME CP-RCM showed good model performance, despite a cold bias for maximum temperature, especially in spring, a dry bias in summer and localised biases in precipitation extremes. The performance of AROME was slightly improved for the incoming SW radiation over continental France, though biases for high altitude regions were still considerable and remained similar to previous runs. Compared to ALADIN, AROME often added value in mountainous regions (except for SW radiation), which made the analysis of the precipitation more difficult as observations are less reliable in these areas. Notably, AROME provided the most added value for hourly precipitation extremes over the southern flank of the Cevennes Mountains and the Mediterranean, where the most intense rainfall occurs in France.

Further studies will be required better understand and evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of CNRM-AROME cy46. In particular, calculating biases in the cloud fraction would be complementary to the SW radiation as it may explain a possible source of bias and indicate directions for future model improvement. Further studies of the added value of the urban model in CNRM-AROME would help to address the question of whether or not increasing model complexity improves bias. The inclusion of rainfall and temperature observations from other European countries beyond France would provide further insight into AROME's performance in different conditions of large-scale circulation, orography and climate.

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